

Date of publication: January 5, 2022

DOI: [10.52270/26585561_2022_13_15_3](https://doi.org/10.52270/26585561_2022_13_15_3)

Historical Sciences

HISTORICAL ASPECTS OF SPORTS-MASS WORK IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS OF RUSSIA

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Abstract

The article examines the historical aspects of the mass sports movement in Russian universities. It should be recognized that during the reform years of the 1990s-2000s, the promotion of a healthy lifestyle and the values of physical culture and sports was carried out haphazardly. The ideal of physical health, the most important component of a lifestyle, has not been formed. Sport as a factor of the country's image remained in oblivion. The multiple increase in the cost of services in the field of physical culture and sports has made the objects of physical culture and sports, tourism and recreation inaccessible to the population of the country. As a result, a healthy lifestyle of people has not acquired the status of moral value. Only in recent years, sport has increasingly acquired the features of one of the directions of state policy and the educational function of public organizations, professional and creative unions.

Keywords: sport, person, health, history, society.

I. INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the topic is due to the fact that physical education of university youth is directly related to the implementation of modern youth and demographic policy in the Russian Federation. The quality of the human and personnel potential of the future Russia depends on the state of physical training of student youth. In this regard, the analysis and generalization of the Soviet experience in the formation of physical culture and sports-mass work among students seems to be topical. Sports collectives of universities at all stages of development of national sports were the vanguard of the physical culture movement and promoters of the mass physical culture movement among urban and rural youth. The transformation of the economy and social sphere is associated with the growing role of the younger generation in the life of Russian society. The youth factor is becoming a determining factor in the domestic community. Health, education, professionalism, general culture and civic maturity of the young generation of Russians determine the quality of labor and defense potential, i.e. the strategy of social and economic development of the Russian Federation. Thus, the success of reforming Russian society largely depends on the "youth factor" and the quality of the juvenile potential.

II. METHODOLOGY AND DISCUSSION

The development of the topic involves the use of various methods of historical research: historical retrospection, system-structural and cultural-historical methods, typology. A special place is occupied by the comparative-comparative method of historical analysis, which makes it possible to reveal the degree of reliability of certain sources, as well as contributing to the reconstruction of a more objective picture of events. The application of this method helps to reveal the features of students' physical education at different stages of the history of the period under consideration. The work implements an interdisciplinary approach, which consists in using in this historical research the achievements, techniques and procedures developed by both the historical and pedagogical sciences. Of the published scientific publications, the article by I.R. Gudzenko is of indisputable interest. Characterizing the state of physical education of students by the end of 1958, the author formulates new tasks of organizing educational and amateur work in connection with the adoption of the "Law on the connection of school with life".

In the work of F.P. Shuvalov, an attempt is made to analyze a relatively long period in the development of physical culture and sports in the universities of the USSR. Starting from a brief historical digression into the history of student sports in pre-revolutionary Russia and in the Soviet period, the author chronologically extends his analysis up to 1959. Based on the analysis of physical education curricula, he traced the evolution of organizational forms and methods of physical education in the post-war period, revealed the features of conducting classes with students of a special preparatory group.

The methodological manual of B.A. Naumov contains some unsystematic information on the history of the development of physical culture in Soviet universities. The author traces the main stages of the development of student sports in the period from 1917 to 1960. However, the article did not reflect such an aspect of the development of physical culture and sports as a factor of improving the student physical culture movement.

Other works consider a number of aspects and topics related to this topic. In his following, V.V. Stolbov briefly described the physical education of schoolchildren and students in schools and universities of the RSFSR. The author traces the main directions of the development of physical culture and sports in the post-war period and the dynamics of their development reflects the pedagogical aspect of the problem. The data presented by the author cover only a short period in the development of student sports. V.G. Mordkovich in his research defends the thesis that the successful solution of the problem of physical education of students depends on the active and purposeful work of public organizations and the university administration, emphasizing the role of physical culture in educating students with organizational skills necessary for their further professional and social activities.

Of the recently published special works, the monograph of Kuznetsova Z.M. deserves attention. The author turns to the history of physical culture. However, the author considers physical education in universities only in passing, without paying special attention to it. The specifics of physical education of the younger generation are not sufficiently reflected.

In the monograph by K.S. Khusnutdinov and A.R. Tuzikov, from the standpoint of historical science, the mechanism of social regulation of mass sports and increasing its importance in the life of modern Russian society has been investigated.

The analysis of the historiography of the problem allows us to conclude that at present there are practically no generalizing studies dedicated to the state and trends in the development of physical education in Russia. Most of the published works have a pedagogical or philosophical orientation, or are devoted to the problems of public administration of mass sports.

III. RESULTS

During the 1940s - 80s, the legal framework for physical education of students was created. The material and technical base has been significantly strengthened, the experience of working with students of various specialties has been accumulated. The achievement, as the analysis showed, was the creation of scientifically based physical education programs that take into account the specializations of university students.

The historical and political factors of the development of physical culture in Russia were the adoption of the Laws "On Education" (1997) and "On Physical Culture and Sports" (1999), the introduction of state educational standards of higher professional education; transformations in the social, economic and political life of Russia taking place at the end of the XX century; the reform of the system of higher professional education.

The development of physical education in universities in the Soviet period was determined by normative documents - resolutions of the party and the government, on the one hand, standard curricula, on the other hand. A retrospective analysis of the programs showed that changes in the forms and methods of physical culture and mass sports work at universities were made approximately every 10-12 years.

The purposefulness and ways of developing physical culture and sports in higher education institutions of the USSR stemmed from the general tasks of the Soviet system of physical education, since students at all stages of the development of higher education were the vanguard of the physical culture movement in the country and a reference point for training specialists in physical culture and sports, for enterprises, institutions, collective farms and state farms.

As a result of the development of student initiative and amateur activity, a new form of physical education has been widely developed — student health and sports camps. It was fixed by sanctioning decisions of state and trade union bodies.

Speaking about the peculiarities of physical education and mass sports work among university students, it should be noted that, in general, the all-Union process was enriched by the cultivation of national sports. The maximum scope, supported by the material base, occurred in 1960 - 1980.

Since the late 1980s, there has been a regression, and the tendency to reduce the network of sports and recreation and sports facilities has become clear, their number has decreased by 20% and did not exceed 198,000. Their one-time capacity was 5 million people, or only 17% of the standard of security. Under the pretext of economic inexpediency, enterprises and organizations refused to maintain sports and recreational facilities, closed, sold, transferred them to other owners or used them for other purposes. After the collapse of the USSR, there were no modern, technically equipped sports bases for some sports in Russia, where you can prepare for performances at the Olympic Games and major international competitions. The volume of domestic production of sporting goods has decreased tenfold. For investors who are ready to invest in physical culture and sports, the corresponding conditions have disappeared. At the beginning of the XXI century. economic processes in Russia have acquired a positive character.

The Central Chernozem region stood out against the background of other regions by the increased intensity of economic and social transformations. This made it possible to pay closer attention to physical culture and sports, including student sports.

The revealed all-Union and all-Russian tendencies were manifested in the system of physical education of university students. The analysis of the work of the departments of physical education revealed the fact of improving the quality of physical education and mass sports work with students in the Soviet period, which was due to the processes of economic growth. At the turn of the 1980s — 1990s, the development of physical education and sports is experiencing difficulties. The positive aspect of these years was the emergence of a humanistic-personal paradigm of physical culture and mass sports work.

IV. CONCLUSION

The restructuring of the education system has given the departments of physical education of universities the task of radically and comprehensively improving the professional training and physical education of future specialists. Changing the target orientation of physical education required abandoning authoritarian methods.

If in the Soviet period the variability and recommendation of normative documents is poorly expressed, at present federal exemplary programs on physical culture are conceptual, advisory, orienting, they are aimed at an independent search for optimal forms, means, methods of physical culture, the development of optimal content in the discipline.

The key positions of updating the system of physical education in higher educational institutions of Russia are democratization and humanization, the development of socio-cultural aspects, the strengthening of educational orientation and the creative development of the values of physical culture.

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ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ СПОРТИВНО-МАССОВОЙ РАБОТЫ В ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЯХ РОССИИ

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Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются исторические аспекты массового спортивного движения в российских вузах. Следует признать, что в годы реформ 1990-2000-х годов пропаганда здорового образа жизни и ценностей физической культуры и спорта осуществлялась бессистемно. Идеал физического здоровья, важнейшая составляющая образа жизни, так и не сформировался. Спорт как фактор имиджа страны остался в забвении. Многократное увеличение стоимости услуг в сфере физической культуры и спорта сделало объекты физической культуры и спорта, туризма и отдыха недоступными для населения страны. В результате здоровый образ жизни людей не приобрел статуса моральной ценности. Только в последние годы спорт все больше приобретает черты одного из направлений государственной политики и воспитательной функции общественных организаций, профессиональных и творческих союзов.

Ключевые слова: спорт, личность, здоровье, история, общество.

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